

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL
SCIENTIFIC TOPICS

OPERATIONS REPORT
OF A THEMATIC MULTISPECTRAL
SCANNER SURVEY
OF 35 SELECTED AREAS OF
THE UNITED KINGDOM
IN 2 PHASES
DURING 1984

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SUMMARY

The Natural Environment Research Council, Scientific Service Division on 25th May 1983 commissioned by telex a 3 phase flying and acquisition of data contract covering 46 individual areas of the United Kingdom where ground research projects by University and N.E.R.C. units were being conducted.

The contract period, covered by this report from availability of equipment, was limited to a 37 day period in 1984 Phase 1 and a 33 day period for the phase 2 1984 flying. At the expiry of these nominated periods, contractual flying and acquisition was terminated, irrespective of whether all areas had been flown.

The aircraft used for the 2 periods of flying was the Navajo Chieftain owned and operated by N.E.R.C. from Kidlington through their handling agents, CSE Aviation Limited.

The following sectionalised report describes the field operation and equipment in detail together with an area by area detail summary of areas flown throughout 1984 called Phase 1 and Phase 2.

PART I

OPERATIONS REPORT

1. INTRODUCTION

The Thematic Scanner Survey described in this report was carried out by Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited on behalf of the Scientific Services Division of Natural Environment Research Council (N.E.R.C.) of Swindon, Wiltshire. The areas surveyed and covered by this report totalled 35 as detailed in Purchase Order F3/G6/229 of 23rd June 1983 and subsequent directives see Text Figures 1 to 10. The 1983 flying covered by this contractual document was the subject of a report presented on completion of that season's flying.

A Piper Navajo/Chieftain aircraft supplied by N.E.R.C. and crewed by CSE Aviation Limited, fitted with a survey camera and a Daedalus AADS1268 Thematic Scanner commenced flying on 19th May 1984 and was terminated on 19th June 1984 (Phase 1), with a further period of flying from 30th August 1984 to 30th September 1984 (Phase II).

The following report describes in detail the acquisition aspects of both phases of this third season of AADS1268 surveying in the United Kingdom.

2. INVOLVED PERSONNEL

N.E.R.C. Co-ordinator and Contractual Representative:-

Dr. David Williams

CSE Aviation Limited:-

Captain/Pilots - H. John
A. Gunter Smith
J. Gledhill (Phase 1 only)

Aircraft Engineers - from CSE pool

Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited:-

Field Project Leader/
Survey Photo Navigator - F.J. Cook

AADS1268 Engineer/
Operators - D.C. Nind
M.P. Conway

Operations Manager - R.D. Williams

3. FLYING OPERATIONS

3.1 Aircraft and Operational Bases

The survey was flown throughout using the N.E.R.C. Chieftain aircraft, registration G-BBXX, based mainly at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport, with landings at Edinburgh, Inverness, RAF Valley, East Midlands, Exeter, Norwich, Humberside and Stornaway Airports, when flying large detailed areas, or long transits were involved.

3.2 Flying Specification and Weather Tolerances

In general the areas to be flown were scattered throughout the United Kingdom and, with the exception of areas in Scotland and the English Channel were flown from the aircraft's base at Kidlington. This base gave the flying crews the best possible servicing facilities and the best photographic dark rooms for quick look processing.

The specifications for height, haze, cloud and flight direction were laid down by N.E.R.C. prior to commencement of the flying programme. These were continually subject to alteration by the client in the light of prevailing weather conditions and availability of field research crews, relative to the maximum contractual availability of the scanner equipment, namely 70 days overall the two periods (see Table 1). The finally achieved flying acquisition details are in Table 2, pages 14, 15, 16.

TABLE 1

Original General Contractual Flying Specification

Weather Restrictions to Flying Programme.

1. Cloud - Sites can be flown in cloud free or under a complete cloud cover. For cloud free up to 5% patchy cloud or shadow can be allowed.

For patchy cloud the site should not be flown without clearance from the N.E.R.C. project co-ordinator.

Sites should not be flown without clearance where the overall luminescence is constantly varying.

2. Precipitation - No restriction due to recent rain is necessary.
3. Wind - Whilst calm conditions are preferable the limiting factor is likely to be turbulence effects on the aircraft.
4. Haze/Visibility - In hazy conditions the scanner operator/crew will be responsible for advising on the likely effect and which

channels will be affected. The N.E.R.C. co-ordinator will then decide. In low light conditions the scanner operator must decide if he can record a satisfactory signal by adjusting the gain.

5. Time - Ideally all flying between 9.30 and 16.00 hours. However, if we get clear mornings and/or clear evenings the N.E.R.C. co-ordinator in conjunction with the crew may alter this.

General

If the aircraft flies and the weather closes in, the principal of flying a target and see should be adopted, rather than returning empty handed.

Photography - 30% forward overlap unless stated otherwise.

Radios

- (i) Can the crew transmit on the aircraft radio so that field teams can listen? they should transmit whilst on target and at the end.
- (ii) The two way radios should be used as needed.
- (iii) Radio silence should be observed with the scanner on and the transponder should be off. These effect the data recording.

Area Covered

The scanner should be switched on for the minimum amount of recording to save data processing.

3.3 Navigation

Other than the standard aircraft navigation aids, no specific navigation equipment was added to the N.E.R.C. survey aircraft. However a survey navigator and a wide angle survey camera were supplied and installed, the camera being used on specific scanner lines. Standard forward overlap was maintained throughout the survey period.

3.4 Survey Diary - Progress and Serviceability

The following is a summary of events during the two phases:-

PHASE 1

MAY 1984

15th Installation of equipment in aircraft commenced at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport.

16th/18th Installation, inspections and tests continued at Kidlington (Oxford) Airport. Office and photographic darkroom set up at airport.

- 19th First 1984 season ATM flight, 9 runs over and around N.E.R.C. Swindon. These have been called A to F G1, G2 and H.
- 20th/23rd No further productive flights due weather.
- 24th 2 sorties flown. 13 runs in total. Danby High Moor 6 runs, Holderness 1 run, Thetford 3 runs, Theobalds Park 3 runs.
- 25th/27th Weather prevented survey. Transit to Scotland carried out.
- 28th 2 sorties flown. Loch Assynt attempted on first flight. Second flight covered Strath Oykel 2 runs. 1 run at low level of Loch Assynt and a further high level attempt of the Loch. 8 runs in total, mostly in variable cloud conditions.
- 29th 2 sorties flown. 16 runs in total covering Loch Levan, Loch Tay, Loch Lomand, Loch Assynt, Straith Oykel and a further low level run of Assynt. Stornaway, Edinburgh, and Inverness airfields were used for this flying period.
- 30th 1 sortie flown comprising 1 run over Holderness. Aircraft returned to Kidlington.
- 31st 1 sortie flown over targets called Didcot B and C. 10 productive runs acquired.
- JUNE
- 1st/3rd No flying due poor weather.
- 4th 2 sorties attempted. AM flight aborted due poor weather. Second sortie achieved 9 runs over Didcot A.
- 5th No flying, poor weather conditions.
- 6th 2 sorties flown. Sortie 1 comprising 2 runs along Bristol Channel. Sortie 2 being 12 runs over Area 1, New Forest.
- 7th No flying, poor weather conditions.
- 8th 4 sorties flown over Swansea Bay area. Flying being conducted in time scheduled blocks with first on line run at 0740 hours and final run at 1745 hours when light began to fade.
- 9th 2 sorties flown, the first being 6 runs in the Snowdonia area. The second sortie comprising 1 run over Anglesey, 3 runs over the Coed-y-Brenin area and a further 5 runs in the Snowdonia region. The aircraft operated out of RAF Valley for these flights.

- 10th 1 sortie flown this being 5 runs in the Sutton Bonnington area. The aircraft landed at Humberside Airport.
- 11th 1 sortie attempted out of Exeter airport. This comprised of 1 run offshore Plymouth.
- 12th/15th Weather prevented survey.
- 16th 2 sorties flown. 8 runs over Hickling Broad, 5 runs over Strumpshaw Marsh, being sortie 1. With 4 runs across Holderness and an aborted attempt at flying Lathkilldale, being sortie 2.
- 17th No flying, due poor weather conditions.
- 18th 1 sortie comprising 9 runs in Lathkilldale area.
- 19th 2 sorties flown. Sortie 1 being the transit flight Lizard/Roscoff/Plymouth/Start Point. Sortie 2 being flights over areas Lizard area B, totalling 10 runs, Crymlyn Bog 3 runs, Cricklade and Fairford 1 run each.
- 20th 1 sortie at low level over Lathkilldale comprising 13 runs. This sortie concluded the flying programme in Phase 1. The equipment being removed from aircraft.

PHASE II

AUGUST

- 17th/19th Equipment to Kidlington and re-mobilisation commenced. Aircraft/equipment ready for initial flight 18th, weather poor.
- 20th 1st productive sortie of Phase 2 flying. Rutland Water flown in poor conditions. Lathkilldale aborted, after one run at 6600 feet, due poor visibility.
- 21st 1 sortie flown comprising Chepstow 2 runs, Swansea 1 run, Crymlyn Bog 3 runs, Dyfid 5 runs, Anglesey 3 runs.
- 23rd/25th Weather prevented survey.
- 26th One sortie flown comprising 10 runs over Lethkilldale.
- 27th Weather prevented survey.
- 28th 1 sortie only flown. Late start due weather. 2 runs over Braunton Burrows.
- 29th 1 sortie flown. 6 runs over Sutton Bonnington. 1 run over Rothampstead.
- 30th Weather prevented survey.

31st 1 sortie. 2 areas flown. Cumbria 2 runs, Danby High Moor 8 runs in poor light.

SEPTEMBER

1st Sortie attempted over Theobalds Park. Aborted due cloud after 2 runs.

2nd 1 sortie. 4 areas flown. Reruns of Theobalds Park 3, Strumpshaw Marsh 5 runs, Acle 4 runs, Thetford 3 runs.

3rd/5th Weather prevented survey flying.

6th 1 sortie attempted over Lathkilldale area - aborted after 4 runs due cloud.

7th/14th Weather prevented survey flying.

15th 2 sorties. 2 areas over New Forest flown. 15 runs in all in Sortie 1. One area Ballantrae, 1 run only flown sortie 2.

16th 1 sortie flown comprising 4 runs over Petersfield.

17th Weather prevented survey flying.

18th 1 sortie flown covering Didcot zones A, B & C and Theale (Reading). Total runs 9 + 5 + 5 + 4 respectively.

19th 1 sortie flown comprising 5 runs over Petersfield.

20th 2 sorties flown. Sortie 1, 2 areas over Durham 6 runs. Sortie 2, 8 runs in and around Theale (Reading). This was the final flight in the 1984 campaign.

During the 2 periods outlined above, weather conditions were less than perfect for ATM flying and a limited number of areas were flown on the insistence of the ground experimental crews, where possible lines known to be affected by poor conditions were further attempted when flights on other acquisition missions were close to the weather affected areas. Overall, only 2 areas remained unflown due to weather conditions, namely Leith in Phase 1 and Holderness in Phase 2.

4. EQUIPMENT

4.1 Survey Camera

The camera used on this year's N.E.R.C. flying was a Wild RC8 wide angle survey camera. This unit was manually operated throughout the survey period by the survey navigator who adjusted the forward overlap to suit the area being surveyed. The camera was installed in the forward camera hole of the N.E.R.C. aircraft and produced throughout 9 x 9 format black/white images. The unit had a 6" focal length and was fitted with a 15 Uag 396 lens. The

processing of all exposed film was carried out in the photo laboratories of Hunting Surveys Limited, Borehamwood, who produced a total of 1,204 prints in Phase 1, and 968 prints in Phase 2, over specified areas. The scale of these prints vary with the differing heights of each area. Photo cover was not commissioned over all areas. A copy of the photo flight logs and an index map of lines flown has been supplied with the survey prints.

4.2 Airborne Thematic Mapper

The equipment chosen for the 1984 N.E.R.C. contract was again the Daedalus Enterprises Inc. AADS 1268 ATM 11 Channel Scanner.

This complete sensor unit comprises a scan head, spectrometer and digitiser coupled in, on this survey, to a AADS 1840 HDDT to B/W film conversion unit, a HDDT playback unit and a Sangamo Sabre III tape recorder, Model 3630 1" machine. This combination of units enabled on site production of HDDTs and Quick Look 5" wide B/W prints of any one selected channel of data at Kidlington. Scan speeds of 12.5, 25 and 50 scans/second were selected for the areas flown and the S bend correction was applied to all areas flown.

The operating wavelengths and performance parameters for the AADS 1268 ATM are as follows:-

TABLE 3

Channel Band Edges in μm	12.5 scans/sec. NER ¹	25 scans/sec. NER ¹	50 scans/sec. NER ¹
0.42 -0.45	0.28	0.36	0.52
*0.45 -0.52	0.06	0.07	0.1
*0.52 -0.60	0.05	0.05	0.05
0.605-0.625	0.10	0.10	0.11
*0.63 -0.69	0.05	0.05	0.05
0.695-0.75	0.05	0.05	0.05
*0.76 -0.90	0.03	0.03	0.03
0.91 -1.05	0.01	0.11	0.15
*1.55 -1.75	0.07	0.1	0.17
*2.08 -2.35	0.005	0.006	0.009
*8.5 -14.0	0.05°	0.07° C	0.08

* Thematic Mapper Bands, except thermal band broadened for aircraft operation.

1. Noise Equivalent Radiance in $w \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$.

Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) 2.5 mrad (1.25 mrad optional)

Digitised Field of View 85.92 degrees (2.5 mr IFOV)
It should be noted that this field of view reduces to 72 degrees when the S Bend correction is applied.

Scan Rates 12.5, 25 and 50 scans/sec.

Velocity/Height Ratio 0.031; 0.062, 0.125
radians/sec. corresponding to
12.5; 25 and 50 scans/sec.,
respectively (2.5 mr IFOV).

Roll Correction $\pm$ 15 degrees

Infrared Reference Source 2 controllable thermal
blackbodies with a temperature
range of -15 to + 50 degrees
centigrade with respect to
scan head heat sink
temperature.

Figure 12 outlines the functional operations of both the scanner head and the spectrometer.

TABLE 4

<u>Primary Channel</u> £	<u>Spectral band in</u> £
1	0.42 - 0.45
2	0.45 - 0.52
3	0.52 - 0.60
4	0.605 - 0.625
5	0.63 - 0.69
6	0.695 - 0.75
7	0.76 - 0.90
8	0.91 - 1.05
9	1.55 - 1.75
10	2.08 - 2.35
11	8.5 -14.0

AADS1268 DIGITAL MSS SYSTEM - SCAN HEAD / SPECTROMETER - OPTICAL DIAGRAM

4.3 Radio Communication Units

8 SMC 317L6 3 watt 6 channel 2 way units were supplied to assist in air/ground movements during proposed area survey period. The radios were again tuned to the licenced frequency of 169.275 Mhz. This licence having previously been allocated to the Hunting Group by the Home Office.

5. DATA ACQUIRED AND PRESENTED

5.1 Onsite

18 High Density Data Tapes (HDDTs) and one channel of B/W prints of quicklook imagery were produced progressively throughout the two survey periods. The HDDTs were carried forward sortie to sortie until a total capacity had been achieved. These was no carry forward of HDDT from period one to two.

9 x 9 photo cover was taken on all lines flown except offshore flights where no landfall was visable. In total 2,172 (1,204 + 968) B/W prints were produced for the 2 flying periods. This does not represent the total number of frames exposed during the flying season as prints of selected areas were omitted from the final selection order.

5.2 Final Presentations

(a) The field produced HDDTs were converted to CCTs in the Hunting laboratories at Elstree on their HP 3000 computer where all channels of data per line flown were recompiled with start and end scans correlated. No flight line was split onto a second tape. The data is presented on the CCTs in the Hunting's band interleaved raw data format (see Table 5).

(b) All photo cover taken throughout the ATM flying has been presented as 9" x 9" black and white prints with their respective negatives. An index plot of the lines flown, showing prints and run numbers, at a scale of 1:50,000 has also been presented.

(c) A report of operations in 5 copies.

5.3 CCT Format

TABLE 5

Huntings Band Interleaved ATM Raw Data Tape Format

9 track
1600 bpi
Binary

Tape blocks will be of constant size within tapes and the size depends on the number of bands. (See aa over page).

(aa)

<u>No Bands</u>	<u>Block size (bytes)</u>	<u>No bands</u>	<u>Block size (bytes)</u>
1	7500	7	10500
2	7500	8	6000
3	9000	9	6750
4	9000	10	7500
5	7500	11	8250
6	9000	12	9000

Logical records of 750 bytes. This is the data for one channel for one scan line including the pre and post amble. The scan format is:-

<u>Byte</u>	<u>Contents</u>
1-4	Start of frame code 01010110 10100101 10100110 10101111
5	Run number/extend line count
6-8	Line count (BCD)
9-12	Thumb Wheel setting (BCD)
13-14	Calibration Source 1 (BCD)
15-16	Calibration Source 2 (BCD)
17-21	External digital data
n.b.	2 msb of byte 17 represent scan speed 00 12.5 scans/sec 01 25 scans/sec 10 50 scans/sec

<u>22</u>	<u>Gain & no S bend</u>	<u>4 msb</u>	<u>Channel</u>	<u>4 lsb</u>
	8	0101	1	0001
	4	0100	2	0010
	2	0011	3	0011
	1	0010	4	0100
	0.5	0001	5	0101
			6	0110
			7	0111
			8	1000
			9	1001
			10	1010
			11	1011
			12	1100

<u>Gain & S bend</u>	<u>4 msb</u>
8	1101
4	1100
2	1011
1	1010
0.5	1001

23 Digitized BB1 (Recorded with gain of 1)
24-739 Video Data
740 Digitized BB1 (Recorded with gain of 1)
741-750 End of frame code
10101010 10101010

Each tape file will contain the data for a complete flight line or for 4000 tape blocks.

Each tape file will start with an ascii header block containing information about the data in that file.

The header block is 576 bytes long and contains 22 lines information. Each line is separated by a carriage return and line feed. The format is described in bb below.

(bb)

<u>Line No.</u>	<u>Length (bytes)</u>	<u>Byte Nos.</u>	<u>Contents</u>
1	40	1- 40	Hunting Geology and Geophysics AAD1268
2	52	41- 92	Clients name
3	13	93-105	Tape nnn
4	23	106-128	Flight date dd- mmm -yy
5	12	129-140	Flight nn
6	34	141-174	Bands n-m-o-p
7	39	175-213	Site - erehwon
8	35	214-248	Scan/Frame count - Start nnnnnnn
9	36	249-284	Scan/Frame count - Finish mmmmmmm
10	30	285-314	Ground clearance nnnn metres
11	25	315-339	Ground speed nnnn knots
12	22	340-361	Pixel nn metres wide
13	22	362-383	Pixel mm metres long
14	17	384-400	750 frame bytes
15	25	401-425	Record size nnnnn bytes
16	24	426-449	Band frame interleaved
17	21	450-470	Video start byte 24
18	20	471-490	Video end byte 739
19	13	491-503	BB1 byte 23
20	14	504-517	BB2 byte 740
21	29	518-546	n.nn milliradian resolution
22	30	547-576	Source HDDT nnn

6. MATERIALS SUPPLIED TO CLIENT

6.1 Survey Film

A total of 2172 9" x 9" black/white survey photographs and their associated negatives covering client selected areas have been supplied.

6.2 Quicklook Imagery

Uncorrected B/W prints of one channel in 5" wide strips along all lines flown were produced from the field equipment and presented to client for inspection.

6.3 CCTs

A total of 307 master CCTs covering all areas flown except, Phase one, Cricklade and Fairford; Phase two, Hickling Broad and Crymlym Bog. 6 CCTs of the 1983 Campaign flown over the Humber Estuary are included in the above total. A duplicate set of Phase 2 CCTs totalling 132 have been supplied as an extra to the above total figure ordered.

6.4 HDDTs

The field produced HDDTs covering all areas flown are held by Huntings pending a directive as to their disposal within the next 12 months.

6.5 Flight Maps

A full set of 1:50,000 scale ordnance survey map sheets of each area flown, with recovered flight line plots superimposed, have been supplied with the photo prints.

6.6 Operations Report

Finally, an outline Operations Report in 5 copies has been presented.

TABLE 2

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT (M/FT)		DIRECTION		GROUND SPEED KMS.	NO. OF RUNS	PHASE FLOWN		DATES FLOWN (1984)	
		P1	P2	P1	P2			P1	P2	P1	P2
1	Loch Assynt	9900		N/S		170	3	*		28/5	
		13200		N/S		160	5			29/5	
2	Lathkilldale	1500	6600	E/W	N	100 150	13 9	*	*	20/6	26/8 &
		6600	1650	E/W	N	160 110	9 1			18/6	6/9
3	Danby Highmoor	6500	6600	N/S	N/S	175 150	5 8	*	*	24/5	31/8
4	Sutton Bonnington	1650	1650			110					
		to	to	N	NW	150	5 5	*	*	10/6	29/8
		13200	9900			140					
5	Western Approaches	13200		N		160	1	*		11/6	
		6600		NE/N/S		170	1 & 2			19/6	
		13200									
6/7	Didcot A,B,C	6600	6600	N/S	N/S	160 150	9 9			4/6	
		6600	6600	NW/SE	EW	160 150	5 5	*	*	31/5	18/9
		6600	6600	NW/SE	NW/SE	160 150	5 5			31/5	
8	Theale (Reading)		800		N/S	125	8	*			20/9
9	Theale (Reading)		6600		N/S	150	3	*			18/9
10	Swansea Bay	13200		E/W		190	16	*		8/6	
	Bristol Channel	13200		NE		200	2	*		6/6	
11	New Forest Area 1	6600	6600	E/W	NW/SE	180 150	12 10	*	*	6/6	15/9
	Area 2	6600	6600	N/S	NE/SW	150	5				
12	Coed-Y-Brenin	13200		N/S		160	3	*		9/6	
13	Ballantrae		13200		SE	150	1	*			15/9
14	Snowdonia	6600		NE/SW		160	11	*		9/6	
				N							
15	Anglesey	2650	2650	NE	NE	150	1	*		9/6	21/8
		2650	2650	E	E	140 150	1 1	*	*		21/8
		2600	2600	NE	NE	150	1				21/8

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT (M/FT)		DIRECTION		GROUND SPEED KMS.	NO. OF RUNS	PHASE FLOWN		DATES FLOWN (1984)	
		P1	P2	P1	P2			P1	P2	P1	P2
16	Cumbia		6600		N	150	2		*		31/8
17	Loch Leven Loch Tay	2600		NW/SE		140	2	*			29/5
		4800		SW		140	1	*			29/5
18	Lizard A & B	9800/ 3300		N/S SE		140 140	2 1	*	*		29/5
		A 13200 B 6600		NW/SE NW/SE		170 170	3 7	*			19/6
21	Braunton Burrows		2650		N	150	1		*		28/8
22	Holderness	3300		S,SE NE		140 160 160	1 1 4	*			30/5,24/5 16/6
		6600		E	E NE/SW	175 150 150	3 3 2	*	*		24/5
24	Thetford Chepstow	6600		E	E E/W	150 150	3 2 3	*	*		24/5
		6600		E	E/W E/W	150 150	3 2 3	*	*		24/5
26	Straith Oykel	13200		N	N	160	1				29/5
		4900		N/S	N/S	160	3	*			29/5
		3300		N	N	140	2				28/5
27	Strumpshaw Hickling Acle	6600		N/S	N/S	160 150	5 5	*	*		16/6
		13200	13200	N/S	N/S	160 150	8 4	*	*		16/6
28	Loch Assynt L/L	3800		N	N	140	2		*		28/5
		3500		N	N	150					29/5
31	Rutland Water	5200		N,NE,W NE		135 110	3 1		*		20/8
		1650									
32	Durham		5000		E/W	150	6		*		20/9
33	Rothamstead		2650		N	140	1		*		29/8

AREA NO.	NAME	HEIGHT (M/FT)		DIRECTION		GROUND SPEED KMS.	NO. OF RUNS	PHASE FLOWN		DATES FLOWN (1984)	
		P1	P2	P1	P2			P1	P2	P1	P2
35	Valley (Swansea)		4000		NE	140	1	*			21/8
36	Dyfid		13200		N/S	160	5	*			21/8
37	Petersfield		6600		N/S	150	4	*			16/9
			6600		N/S	150	5				19/9
38	Crymlyn Bog	3300	3300	E/W	W	150	3	*		19/6	21/8
						160	3				
39	Cricklade	2200		E		150	1	*		19/6	
40	Fairford	2650		E		150	1	*		19/6	
41	Swindon - Tests	2300 to 2650		W N NE/SW		150	9	*		19/5	

PART II

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Loch Assynt 1	Map Sheet Nos.	O/S 15
Flying Height (feet)	9900 13200	Direction Flown	N/S
Flight Conditions	Good visibility some cloud	No. of Lines	5
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	99	No. of Scan Lines	19570
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	5
Ground Speed (knots)	170 160	Scan Speed rps	12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	1145/1203, 1356/1440	Tape Footage	1593
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Lath Kill Dale 2	Map Sheet Nos.	O/S 119
Flying Height (feet)	P1 = 1500/6600 P2 = 1650/6600	Direction Flown	P1 = E/W P2 = N/S
Flight Conditions	P1 = Poor vis, variable cloud/hazy P2 = very Hazy 3/8 cloud	No. of Lines	P1 = 9 P2 = 10
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	P1=64 P2=92	No. of Scan Lines	P1 = 34,842 P2 = 42,075
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	P1 = 11 P2 = 13
Ground Speed (Knots)	P1 = 160/170 P2 = 150/100	Scan Speed rps	P1 = 25/50 P2 = 25/50
Time Flown (GMT)	P1 = 0900/1010 1210/1246 P2 = 1138/1332 1208/1241	Tape Footage	P1 = 5025 P2 = 3222
Research Team Availability	Yes	"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Danby High Moor 3	Map Sheet Nos.	O/S 94
Flying Height (Feet.)	P1 = 6500/P2 = 6600	Direction Flown	N/S N/S
Flight Conditions	P1 = Good /P2 = very dark due Highcloud	No. of Lines	6 8
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	37 37	No. of Scan Lines	13,999 17,212
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	6 8
Ground Speed (knots)	P1 = 175 P2 = 150	Scan Speed rps	25 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1132 - 1205 1608 - 1636	Tape Footage	710 875
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Sutton Bonnington 4	Map Sheet Nos.	O/S 129
Flying Height (feet)	P1 = 1650 to 13,200 P2 = 1650 to 9900	Direction Flown	N N/W
Flight Conditions	P1 = Good P2 = 3/8 Cloud at 4000 Haze	No. of Lines	5 6
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	25 105	No. of Scan Lines	6960 8444
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	5 6
Ground Speed (Knots)	150 110 -140	Scan Speed rps	25/50 125/25/50 12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	1130/1215 1203 - 1334	Tape Footage	384 574
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Western Approaches 5	Map Sheet Nos.	-
Flying Height (Feet)	P1 = 13200/6600/13200	Direction Flown	N/NE/S
Flight Conditions	Sun Glare	No. of Lines	4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	101	No. of Scan Lines	56,222
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	16
Ground Speed (knots)	160/170	Scan Speed rps	12.5/25
Time Flown (GMT)	1606/1616. 1214/1348	Tape Footage	3183
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Didcot ABC 6/7	Map Sheet Nos.	O/S 174
Flying Height (feet)	P1 = 6600 P2 = 6600	Direction Flown	P1 SE/NW,N/S N/S, EW, NWS
Flight Conditions	P1 = some cloud/Haze P2 = Cloud below A/C	No. of Lines	19 19
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	96 83	No. of Scan Lines	P1 =35471 P2 =39295
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	19 19
Ground Speed (Knots)	160 150	Scan Speed rps	25 25
Time Flown (GMT)	P1 = 1055/1150 1340/1431 P2 = 1047 1202	Tape Footage	2034 1992
Research Team Availability	YES	"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Theale 8	Map Sheet Nos.	0/S 175
Flying Height (feet)	P2 = 800	Direction Flown	N/S
Flight Conditions	Very Poor conditions	No. of Lines	8
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	144	No. of Scan Lines	38,187
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	14
Ground Speed (knots)	125	Scan Speed rps	50
Time Flown (GMT)	1641 - 1728	Tape Footage	2084
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Theale 9	Map Sheet Nos.	0/S 175
Flying Height (.feet)	P2 = 6600	Direction Flown	N/S
Flight Conditions	Cloud Below A/C	No. of Lines	3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	5	No. of Scan Lines	6517
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	3
Ground Speed (Knots)	150	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	1025 - 1038	Tape Footage	361
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name Swansea Bay /Bristol Channel 10 Map Sheet Nos. O/S 159, 170, 171
 Flying Height (Feet) P1 = 13200 Direction Flown NE/ & E/W
 Flight Conditions Good No. of Lines 2 + 16
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints 131 No. of Scan Lines 78,644
 Film Forward Overlap (%) 30 No. of CCTs 20 + 3
 Ground Speed (knots) 180/190/200 Scan Speed rps 12.5
 Time Flown (GMT) 1134 - 1216 0740 0928 1121 1155 Tape Footage 4247
 1326 - 1539 1739 - 1745
 Research Team Availability "S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
 Camera Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
 Scanner Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
 Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
 unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name New Forest Areas 1 & 2 11 Map Sheet Nos. O/S 195/6
 Flying Height (Feet) P1 = 6600 Direction Flown N,S,E,W,
 P2 = 6600 NW SE NE SW
 Flight Conditions Good, Thincloud cover initially, No. of Lines 12 15
 getting worse
 No. of 9" x 9" photo prints 50 53 No. of Scan Lines 22618
 27,929
 Film Forward Overlap (%) 30 No. of CCTs 12 15
 Ground Speed (Knots) 180 150 Scan Speed rps 25 25
 Time Flown (GMT) P1 = 1428 - 1533 Tape Footage 1131 1524
 P2 = 0947 - 1048
 Research Team Availability YES "S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
 Camera Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
 Scanner Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic
 Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter
 unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Coed-y-Brenim 12	Map Sheet Nos.	O/S 124
Flying Height (Feet)	P1 13200	Direction Flown	N/S
Flight Conditions	Some Cloud Hazy	No. of Lines	3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	40	No. of Scan Lines	5912
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	3
Ground Speed (knots)	160	Scan Speed rps	12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	1546 - 1601	Tape Footage	297
Research Team Availability	YES	"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Ballantrae 13	Map Sheet Nos.	76
Flying Height (Feet)	13,200	Direction Flown	SE
Flight Conditions	GOOD	No. of Lines	1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	9	No. of Scan Lines	1669
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	1
Ground Speed (Knots)	150	Scan Speed rps	12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	14 40/1442	Tape Footage	94
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Snowdonia 14	Map Sheet Nos.	114/5
Flying Height (Feet)	6600	Direction Flown	NE/SE & N
Flight Conditions	Haze	No. of Lines	5 + 6
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	69	No. of Scan Lines	12,730
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	5
Ground Speed (knots)	160	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	1149 - 1232 1503 - 1526	Tape Footage	645 + 604
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Anglesey 15	Map Sheet Nos.	114 115
Flying Height (Feet)	2650 2650	Direction Flown	NE & NE E
Flight Conditions	Haze. Dull/turbulent /haze	No. of Lines	1 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	22 23	No. of Scan Lines	2344 4862
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	1 & 3
Ground Speed (Knots)	140 150	Scan Speed rps	50 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1438 - 1445	Tape Footage	244 376
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Cumbria 16	Map Sheet Nos.	97
Flying Height (Feet)	6600	Direction Flown	N
Flight Conditions	Some Cloud Fair	No. of Lines	2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	17	No. of Scan Lines	3328
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	2
Ground Speed (knots)	150	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	1526 -1531	Tape Footage	170
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Lochs Leven/Tay/Lomand 17	Map Sheet Nos.	51/2 56 57/58
Flying Height (Feet)	2600 4800 9800/3300	Direction Flown	NW/SE SW S, N, SE
Flight Conditions	Overhead Cloud/Generally Dark	No. of Lines	2 1 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	44 37 52	No. of Scan Lines	8553 9024 16973
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	2 1 3
Ground Speed (Knots)	140 140 140	Scan Speed rps	50 25 12.5 & 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1003 -1008 1034 - 1040 1107 - 1138	Tape Footage	440 453 853
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES YES YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	LIZARD A & B 18	Map Sheet Nos.	a = 204 b = -
Flying Height (Feet)	A 13200 B 6600	Direction Flown	a = SW,NE B = SW,NE
Flight Conditions	Very Hazy, Turbulent	No. of Lines	a = 3 b = 7
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	a = 28 b = -	No. of Scan Lines	a = 6442 b = -
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	a = 3 b = -
Ground Speed (knots)	a = 170 b = 170	Scan Speed rps	a = 12.5 b = 25
Time Flown (GMT)	a = 1611 - 1628 b = 1530 - 1556	Tape Footage	a = 325 b = .646
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Braunton Burrows 21	Map Sheet Nos.	180
Flying Height (Feet)	2650	Direction Flown	N
Flight Conditions	Bright Clear	No. of Lines	2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	19	No. of Scan Lines	2958
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	2
Ground Speed (Knots)	150	Scan Speed rps	50
Time Flown (GMT)	1604 - 1610	Tape Footage	157
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	HOLDERNESS 22	Map Sheet Nos.	101/107
Flying Height (Feet)	3300	Direction Flown	SE, S, NE
Flight Conditions	Generally Good	No. of Lines	1 1 4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	23	No. of Scan Lines	- - 6650
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	- - 5
Ground Speed (knots)	160 140 160	Scan Speed rps	50 25 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1204-1205 1210-1211 1541-1603	Tape Footage	627
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Thetfold/Chepstow 24	Map Sheet Nos.	171 143/4 162/171
Flying Height (Feet)	6600 6600 6600	Direction Flown	E, E, NE, SW
Flight Conditions	Good. Some cloud, Haze/Cloud Dull	No. of Lines	3 3 2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	60 37 54	No. of Scan Lines	13, 132 10,597 12,33
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	3 3 2
Ground Speed (Knots)	175 150 150	Scan Speed rps	25 25 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1524 - 1522 1144-1206 1034 - 1045	Tape Footage	661 534 619
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES YES YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Theobalds Park 25	Map Sheet Nos.	166 166
Flying Height (Feet)	6600 6600	Direction Flown	E EW
Flight Conditions	Good, Clear Good	No. of Lines	3 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	56 32	No. of Scan Lines	11,410, 12,237
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	3 3
Ground Speed (knots)	175 150	Scan Speed rps	25 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1621 - 1647, 0924 - 0938	Tape Footage	576 616
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Straith Oykel 26	Map Sheet Nos.	15/16
Flying Height (Feet)	13,200 & 4900	Direction Flown	N,S
Flight Conditions	Very good	No. of Lines	4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	37	No. of Scan Lines	5357
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	3
Ground Speed (Knots)	160	Scan Speed rps	12.5 & 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1444 - 1506	Tape Footage	351
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	a. Strumpshaw c. Acle	b. Hickling	27	Map Sheet Nos.	a=138 b=134 c=134
Flying Height (Feet)	a = 6600 c = 13200	b = 13200		Direction Flown	a=N/S b=N/S c=N/S
Flight Conditions	a = Bright Haze c = Good	b = Bright Haze		No. of Lines	a=5 b=8 c=4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	a 34	b 32	c 18	No. of Scan Lines	a=13,225 b=9787 c=8556
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30			No. of CCTs	a=5 b=8 c=4
Ground Speed (knots)	a=160	b=160	c=150	Scan Speed rps	a=25 b=12.5 c=12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	a=1202/1233 c=1058-1120	b=1249/1336		Tape Footage	a=698 b=559 c=429
Research Team Availability				"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Loch Assynt L/L	28	Map Sheet Nos.	15
Flying Height (Feet)	3500		Direction Flown	N
Flight Conditions	Very good		No. of Lines	1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	6		No. of Scan Lines	16,384
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30		No. of CCTs	5
Ground Speed (Knots)	150		Scan Speed rps	50
Time Flown (GMT)	1520-1525		Tape Footage	824
Research Team Availability			"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name Rutland Water	31	Map Sheet Nos. 130/141
Flying Height (Feet)	1650/5200	Direction Flown N,W, NE
Flight Conditions	Very Bad Haze	No. of Lines 4
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	52	No. of Scan Lines 15916
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs 5
Ground Speed (knots)	110/135	Scan Speed rps 50/25
Time Flown (GMT)	1159-1246	Tape Footage 831
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name Durham 1 & 2	32	Map Sheet Nos. 88/93
Flying Height (Feet)	1 = 5000 2 = 5000	Direction Flown 1 E,W 2 E,W
Flight Conditions	1 Clear/Bright 2 Some Cloud Below A/C	No. of Lines 1 = 3 2 = 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	1 = 15 2 = 23	No. of Scan Lines 1 = 4417 2 = 5272
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs 1 = 3 2 = 3
Ground Speed (Knots)	1 = 150 2 = 150	Scan Speed rps 1 = 25 2 = 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1 = 1134 - 1141 2 = 1151 - 1202	Tape Footage 1 = 225 2 = 355
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Rothamstead 33	Map Sheet Nos.	166
Flying Height (Feet)	2650	Direction Flown	N
Flight Conditions	3/8 Cloud at 4000 Haze	No. of Lines	2
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	13	No. of Scan Lines	1778
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	2
Ground Speed (knots)	140	Scan Speed rps	50
Time Flown (GMT)	1412 - 1416	Tape Footage	98
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Valley (Swansea) 35	Map Sheet Nos.	159
Flying Height (Feet)	4000	Direction Flown	NE
Flight Conditions	Very Hazy	No. of Lines	1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	13	No. of Scan Lines	2329
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	1
Ground Speed (Knots)	140	Scan Speed rps	25
Time Flown (GMT)	1109-1111	Tape Footage	118
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Dyfid 36	Map Sheet Nos.	135
Flying Height (Feet .)	13200	Direction Flown	N/S
Flight Conditions	Very Hazy	No. of Lines	5
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	16	No. of Scan Lines	4945
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	5
Ground Speed (knots)	160	Scan Speed rps	12.5
Time Flown (GMT)	1202 - 1228	Tape Footage	249
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Petersfield 37	Map Sheet Nos.	197
Flying Height (Feet .)	6600 6600	Direction Flown	N,S
Flight Conditions	Some Cloud, very Hazy. 1/8 Cloud Below A/C	No. of Lines	4 5
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	Not Produced 47	No. of Scan Lines	approx 16200 15165
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30	No. of CCTs	Not produced, 5
Ground Speed (Knots)	150 150	Scan Speed rps	25 25
Time Flown (GMT)	1006 - 1022 1038 - 1101 1131-1151 (less cloud rerun)	Tape Footage	597 772/766
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Crymlyn Bog 38	Map Sheet Nos.	170
Flying Height (Feet)	3300 3300	Direction Flown	E/W W
Flight Conditions	Very Hazy bad Visibility. very hazy	No. of Lines	3 3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	17 Not Produced.	No. of Scan Lines	3828 approx: 6000
Film Forward Overlap (%)	30 -	No. of CCTs	2 Not produced
Ground Speed (knots)	150 160	Scan Speed rps	50 50
Time Flown (GMT)	1713 - 1720 1120 - 1131	Tape Footage	310 303
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name	Cricklade 39	Map Sheet Nos.	163
Flying Height (Feet)	2200	Direction Flown	E
Flight Conditions	Very hazy bad visibility	No. of Lines	1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	Not produced	No. of Scan Lines	Approx 900
Film Forward Overlap (%)	-	No. of CCTs	Not produced
Ground Speed (Knots)	150	Scan Speed rps	50
Time Flown (GMT)	1755 - 1756	Tape Footage	39
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

NERC 1984 SURVEY

Phase 1 and 2

Area No. and Name	Fairford 40	Map Sheet Nos.	163
Flying Height (Feet)	2650	Direction Flown	E
Flight Conditions	Very hazy bad visibility	No. of Lines	1
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints	Not produced	No. of Scan Lines	approx 800
Film Forward Overlap (%)	-	No. of CCTs	Not produced
Ground Speed (knots)	150	Scan Speed rps	50
Time Flown (GMT)	1801 - 1802	Tape Footage	35
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

Area No. and Name		Map Sheet Nos.	
Flying Height (metres)		Direction Flown	
Flight Conditions		No. of Lines	
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints		No. of Scan Lines	
Film Forward Overlap (%)		No. of CCTs	
Ground Speed (Knots)		Scan Speed rps	
Time Flown (GMT)		Tape Footage	
Research Team Availability		"S" Bend Correction	YES

Aircraft	NERC Navajo Chieftain GBBXX
Camera	Wild RC8 Wide Angle 6" 15 Uag 396 lens
Scanner	Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

NOT USED

FIGURE 2

Incape or
Belt Rock

17

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FIGURE 6

15 DUBLIN
 16 WEXFORD
 17 WICK
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FELIXSTOWE
Zebrugg
Gothsburg

HARWICH to
Hook of Holland 61.6;
B. 131.7

MILES	KILOMETRES
0	0
10	16
20	32
30	48
40	64
50	80
60	96
70	112
80	128
90	144
100	160

5	PLIMM
10	PLIMM
15	PLIMM
20	PLIMM
25	PLIMM
30	PLIMM
35	PLIMM
40	PLIMM
45	PLIMM
50	PLIMM
55	PLIMM
60	PLIMM
65	PLIMM
70	PLIMM
75	PLIMM
80	PLIMM
85	PLIMM
90	PLIMM
95	PLIMM
100	PLIMM

- 0 118 LIVERPOOL
- 2 84 35 MANCHESTER
- 37 159 155 132 NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE
- 19 105 220 185 264 NORWICH
- 5 35 98 63 157 122 NOTTINGHAM
- 3 124 157 144 260 145 98 OXFORD
- 42 293 283 283 410 343 267 185 PLYMOUTH
- 50 201 234 221 337 186 175 77 164 PORTSMOUTH
- 62 46 72 38 125 146 37 135 283 212 SHEFFIELD
- 34 117 58 69 201 205 82 106 225 185 82 SHREWSBURY
- 37 188 221 208 324 193 162 64 151 21 199 170 SOUTHAMPTON
- 07 282 221 220 158 390 290 362 500 438 263 277 425 STRANRAER
- 58 209 153 187 319 274 169 141 206 182 200 118 161 374 SWANSEA
- 08 75 99 64 84 181 77 181 333 258 52 133 242 251 YORK

(ST MARY'S) (24 hrs)
 Wolf Rock

FIGURE 11

11 miles
18.000
10 110 90 80 70 60 50 40 30

THE P

12 miles
19.300
10 110 90 80 70 60 50 40 30

14 miles
22.500
10 110 90 80 70 60 50 40 30

14 miles
22.500
10 110 90 80 70 60 50 40 30

50
4
10 110 90 80 70 60 50 40 30

FIELD
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DOUGLAS to
Belfast
Dublin

41 hrs	(seasonal)
41 hrs	(seasonal)

LIVERPOOL to
Dublin
Belfast

7-8 hrs	10 hrs
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ANGLESEY
1108
10

Point Lynas
Great Ormes Head
Penarth

Hunting Geology and Geophysics' Airborne Thematic Mapper makes the Company A WORLD LEADER

The purchase by Hunting Geology and Geophysics of the world's most advanced airborne multispectral scanner confirms the company's leading position in remote sensing.

With the advancement of technology and in order to maintain the Company's role of a world leader in this field, last year HG&G took delivery of a Daedalus Enterprises Inc airborne multispectral scanner, the AADS 1268. This purchase, together with ancillary equipment, represented an investment of nearly £0.5 million.

The scanner is known as the Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) and was developed as a support system for NASA's Thematic Mapper Satellite. The scanner has 11 channels which take measurements in the visible and thermal infra red parts of the electromagnetic spectrum and is an extremely effective means of rapidly undertaking inventory and monitoring work from the air. It is readily installed in any aircraft that has a standard survey camera hole.

The ATM provides detailed information of surface characteristics and environmental changes. Landsat data are more suited to regional and reconnaissance roles. [continued overleaf]

Heathrow (Pictures 1 and 2)
The ATM was flown across London from Heathrow to the Thames Barrier on 5 September 1983. Imaging was continuous over the 37 km, the data from the 11 spectral channels being recorded on high density digital tape (HDDT).

Picture 1 is produced from the thermal infra red channel of the scanner which records heat differences. This information is not directly perceived by the eye.

Picture 2 is produced by combining three of the visible bands recorded by the scanner. Field's Executive Jet Centre occupies the bottom left hand corner and Concorde's distinctive shape identifies it from other aircraft.

Interestingly, while there is no aircraft on the tarmac alongside Concorde, two are plainly seen next to her in the thermal image. These are thermal shadows still retained by the apron although the aircraft responsible have since been moved. There are numbers of other similar ghosts to be seen in other bays.

Various combinations of other spectral channels emphasise different features, e.g. repairs and chronology of concrete work, disturbed ground and conduit routes.

The River Gilpin, Cumbria (Pictures 7 and 8)

A combination of the visible and the thermal bands introduce improved discrimination in crops and vegetation of the saltings. The darker blues show more vigorous evapotranspiration among green-leaved vegetation.

Picture 8 is the same scene as 7, subjected to 16 class unsupervised computer classification. The computer is able to decide upon, and discriminate, spectral units with a consistency impossible for the human interpreter, but it still remains for an interpreter to categorise the features.

Only three of these instruments have been built and that now owned by Huntings is the only one available outside the USA. This scanner is applicable to many kinds of research. For example, ATM data can give important information for petroleum and mineral exploration: the middle infra red band is particularly sensitive to clay minerals often associated with certain mineral deposits.

The scanner has been very busy ever since Hunting took delivery. On arrival in Britain, it immediately commenced a multi-site programme for the Natural Environment Research Council, followed by a variety of other jobs in the UK. In January this year HG&G used it for a 30 day project in Australia and moved it from there to the Middle East. On return to the UK, more multi-site work was carried out in Britain interspersed with visits abroad.

These illustrations, taken from some of the projects, show how easy it is to make fundamental deductions at a glance. The pictures are not registered instantaneously, but are built up by the scanning process, somewhat similarly to a TV image.

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Swansea Valley South Wales (Picture 5)
A combination of infra red and visible bands shows species/planting chronology differentiation in the wooded lands. The yellow areas are of a computer classified unit, i. e. all areas of a selected combination of spectral characteristics have been identified by the computer program and coded in this yellow colour.

This image is by courtesy of Drs Coulson and Bridges, Swansea University. The university project, sponsored by the Natural Environment Research Council, examined the potential of the ATM for monitoring progress in reclamation of derelict land.

Western Australia (Picture 6)
The Western Australian outback is rich in gold, nickel and other metals. This image, covering about 80 km², is about 30 km northwest of Kalgoorlie. An advanced statistical program (principal component analysis) run on HIPAS for the area assists

the interpretation. Additional rock units to those identifiable on standard imagery are readily differentiated in this special process, e.g. in the arcuate unit (top right) in which volcanic and sedimentary formations occur together.

The combination of the advanced multi-spectral scanner, the Daedalus AADS 1268, and the fast interactive image processor, HIPAS, considerably aids the mapping of rocks and, in this case, directly contributes to mineral exploration. Some of the anomalous hues and associations may be related to mineralisation.

The ATM survey of Western Australia covered 30,000 km² of the mineral rich Archaean craton, mostly the Wiluna-Norseman Greenstone Belt. The whole survey, a joint effort of HG&G Australia and HG&G UK, took 30 days from conception to completion. It was the first ATM survey over a Precambrian Shield area for the purposes of mineral exploration.

Dockland and the Thames Barrier

(Picture 3)

The image here has been produced by a 16 class unsupervised automatic classification program of the Hunting Image Processing and Analysis System (HIPAS). It has distinguished very effectively the turbulence patterns produced by the Thames Barrier. The Barrier has gates set in the river floor which can be raised to hold back flood surges that periodically come up the river and threaten to inundate low lying areas in the capital. A sequence of images at different tide states would illustrate the effects on river flow produced by the Barrier. The water in the dock is dense black, there being no reflections from suspended sediments as particles have settled to the bottom in the still water. Appropriate processing can nevertheless bring out localised differences in the dock water.

Humberside (Picture 4)

The ATM Scanner was flown over the Humber at the time of a major oil slick. Picture 4, simulated true colour, is a spectacular view of the polluted river.